

Effect of Interactive Whiteboard on Academic Performance of Secondary School Mathematics Students in Rivers State

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of Interactive whiteboard on academic performance of secondary school Mathematics students in Rivers State. The study adopted the quasi-experimental research design using non-randomized-control group-pre-test and post-test experimental group design. The population of the study is 40,497 students across 247 senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The Stratified random sampling technique was used to select a sample size of one hundred (100) students. The instrument for data collection is Mathematics Performance Test (MPT). The MPT had ten (10) items questions. The face and content validity of the Mathematics Performance Test (MPT) was established by two experts in mathematics education and one in test and measurement. Kuda-Richardson (KR-21) method was used to test for the reliability of the instrument (MPT) and a reliable value was 0.73. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significant levels. The results of the findings revealed that: the experimental group demonstrated a more significant improvement in mathematics performance compared to the control group, the improvement was more noticeable among female students, though this difference was not statistically significant. The following recommended were made: Mathematics teachers should infuse interactive whiteboards into their teaching and learning, as this approach could improve students' mathematics achievement of students. Mathematics teachers should also ensure equal opportunity for gender in order to limit gender discrepancies for equal access to interactive whiteboards in their classrooms.

Keywords: Interactive White board, academic performance and Mathematics achievement

Introduction

Teaching techniques, instructional materials and methods of teaching used by Mathematics teachers and students towards the concept can contribute to learners' inability to understand and retain basic Mathematics procedures, calculations and applications; they can contribute to the low achievement of students in solving Mathematics problems. Based on this, Mathematics instructors have been searching for appropriate ways of solving the existing increase of failure in Mathematics. It is currently observed that there are preferable ways of learning Mathematics that are better than the conventional practice. Mathematics is an important subject that applies to all facets of life. Everyone in society makes use of Mathematics daily may be wordy including market men and women. The role played by Mathematics in all areas of development in life cannot be overemphasized. It serves as a backbone to all technological advancement in the world. There can be no meaningful development in this modern world of the technological era without adequate knowledge of Mathematics. The study of Mathematics enhances one's understanding of the world through the use of symbols and abstract representation of phenomena (Burton, 2012). Many things have changed in the twenty-first century as a result of the advent of new developing technologies, including the techniques and methods of teaching and learning in the classroom. With the development of new technologies, there is a paradigm shift from traditional methods of teaching and learning to a

technologically oriented pattern that encourages collaboration and student-centered learning. Technology not only engages students, assists teachers in differentiating their education, and fosters connections that would otherwise be unattainable, but it also prepares them to adapt to a rapidly changing technologically oriented society (Makanya, 2015). Not to mention the fact that technology aids in organization, lesson planning, and classroom management.

The invention of technology has been a blessing in present times in teaching and learning. Technologies like cell phones, overhead slides, wireless internet access, interactive whiteboards, graphing calculators, laptop computers, tablets, and other evolving technologies have been deployed by teachers in one way or the other to teach chemistry concepts. As such, teachers may use technology to boost their productivity, incorporate valuable digital tools to extend students' learning opportunities and increase student support and involvement. It also allows teachers to improve their teaching techniques and customize learning (Ode, 2014). The Interactive Whiteboard (IWB) is a large, touch-sensitive board, connected to a computer and to a projector that offers an attractive colorful picture, and enables manipulating texts by deleting, coloring and saving them, including combining pictures, applications, programming, web pages and so on. The use of the IWB increased in recent years in schools around the world, and its popularity has been enhanced amongst many teachers (Murcia, 2014). The IWB penetrated schools in England most in comparison to other countries around the world.

An Interactive Whiteboard (IWB) is an instructional technology for computer graphics which projected onto a board with the help of a digital projector ((Murcia, 2014). The instructor can manipulate the objects on the board using the mouse directly on the screen while utilizing IWB. Similarly, items can be dragged, clicked, and copied, and the instructor can handwrite notes, which can then be converted to text format and saved.

The interactive whiteboard has become more relevant in several areas of the academic environment, serving as a veritable instrument for learning (Betcher & Lee, 2019). In some classrooms, interactive whiteboards have taken the place of traditional whiteboards or flipcharts, as well as video/media devices such as DVD players and TVs (Reardon, 2012). Even in situations where traditional boards are employed, the IWB is frequently used to enhance them by linking to a school network digital video distribution system. In other circumstances, IWBs connect with online collaborative annotation and drawing environments, such as interactive vector-based graphical webpages.

Regardless of the numerous educational technologies that have the potential to improve science teaching and learning, the quality of science teaching and learning in Nigeria is a source of concern for everybody (Gillen et al., 2018). Science education at all levels continues to take the traditional conservative approach, with the teacher serving as the purveyor of knowledge and the students as the passive recipients. Students' involvement is limited in a traditional demonstration-based teaching environment because teachers typically use teaching methods that focus on information delivery and knowledge acquisition rather than encouraging the building of knowledge within the social context.

Most of the time, the traditional demonstration is delivered in a one-way communication format, with few possibilities for class debate and active student participation. In a typical Nigerian science classroom setting, where expository and unproductive teaching methods are frequently observed studies confirmed that traditional science teaching still heavily relies on lectures, reading, and teacher demonstrations (Agogo & Onda, 2014), these teaching strategies are likely to be inadequate and inappropriate to achieve Mathematics learning. As a result, the prevalent use of teacher-centered

teaching methods may make understanding the concept challenging, particularly when the topic taught is not only complex but also abstract and dynamic.

Academic performance is the extent to which a student has attained their short or long-term educational goals. The observed students' poor performance and weaknesses in Mathematics in Nigeria are a result of several factors among inadequate teaching methods seen to be the most prominent in determining students' success have piqued the interest of academic researchers from a variety of disciplines (Agogo, 2013). They attempted to establish which variables have a favorable and negative impact on student performance. The significance of students' performance is obvious not only to the students but also to the school, as it is a measure of the success of their educational process. The teaching of Mathematics is not left out in the use of digital pedagogy.

Ifeakor, Akujize, and Erutujiro (2020) determine the effect of an interactive whiteboard-based instructional model on students' academic achievement in mathematics in Onitsha North L.G.A of Anambra State. The study employed a quasi-experimental design. The sample for this study comprised one hundred SS2 Students. Two intact classes consisting of fifty students were randomly assigned to the experimental and fifty to the control group. The experimental group was taught mathematics using the interactive whiteboard instructional model while the control group was taught mathematics using the lecture method. Three research questions guided the study. Three null hypotheses were formulated and tested at a .05 level of significance with analyses of covariance (ANCOVA). The instrument Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) was constructed, and validated and reliability of internal consistency was established (.87) using K-R 20 before data collection. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested at ($P < .05$) using analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). The result revealed that the interactive whiteboard-based instructional model is superior to the lecture method in improving achievement among the students in mathematics. Based on these, some recommendations were made which include; that seminars and workshops should be organized by the government and relevant professional bodies like ASSEREN, and STAN to educate and sensitize the teachers on the proper use of the interactive whiteboard-based instructional model. An urgent curriculum review to reflect the Nigerian culture and environment in the secondary school curriculum was also recommended.

In a different study under the problem-based learning category, Onyeagwu (2019) focused on the effect of Gagne's signal and stimulus-response learning hierarchy model on students' performance in mathematics. The purpose of the study was to find out the amount of mastery, retention and transfer of learned skills in mathematical concepts. Three null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The quasi-experimental design was used for this study. The sample was made up of 240 students from six schools from the three senatorial districts of Delta State. Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT), Test of Retention (TOR) and Test of Transfer (TOT) were the instruments used for data collection. The data collected were analyzed using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to determine the direction of the result. The findings among others revealed that the application of signal and stimulus-response learning hierarchy has higher performance on the MAT than the conventional method and also more intellectual skills were retained and transferred.

According to Lewin, Somekh, and Steadman (2018), as technology increased in classrooms, available to use whenever they wished to do so, there was a huge increase in teachers' information and communication technology skills over two years. There was also an observable process of eagerly continuing professional development to enhance their technological literacy for instruction.

The new information and communication technology has opened classrooms to the world. “The use of multimedia can create a classroom without walls” (Hall & Higgins, 2015).

Glover, and Miller (2017) identified three teaching approaches in classrooms equipped with an interactive whiteboard. Of the observed lessons, Glover and Miller (2017) found that teachers used a supported didactic approach, using the board as a visual aid, in 14 lessons, an interactive approach, using the board as a visual, verbal, and kinaesthetic aid, in 15 lessons, and an enhanced interactivity approach in 21 of the lessons. Wood and Ashfield (2008) point out that interactive whiteboards promote more direct teaching techniques such as "explaining, modeling, directing, and instructing." While the boards can promote new teaching and learning opportunities, Wood and Ashfield (2008) also point out that a teacher's perception, understanding, and interpretation of teaching and learning have a more significant impact on student learning, rather than the tools being used or not used.

Ikwuka and Samuel (2017) investigated the effect of computer animation on Chemistry academic achievement of secondary school students in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria. A quasi-experimental pre-test, post-test nonequivalent control group design was used for the study. The sample for the study comprised 100 SS2 students from two randomly selected co-educational secondary schools. One of the schools was assigned to the experimental condition, and the other was assigned to the control condition. The instrument known as the Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT), validated by three experts with a reliability coefficient of 0.82 was used for data collection. The CAT was used as a pretest and posttest for both experimental and control groups. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while ANCOVA was used to test the null hypotheses at $P < 0.05$. The result revealed that computer animation Chemistry instruction CACI had a significant effect on students' academic achievement in Chemistry; and that gender had a significant effect on the academic achievement in Chemistry of male and female students who were taught CACI in favour of males. The finding implies that there is a need for Chemistry teachers to use CACI in teaching Chemistry. Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that computer animation instruction (CACI) should be adopted by Chemistry teachers for teaching chemical concepts to secondary school students. Also, other instructional materials like computers, storage devices, and projectors should be made available for the Chemistry teachers to prepare and teach their lessons. The use of animation in the teaching of chemical reactions as used in this study added real value to the teaching of chemistry, not only did it increase students' understanding of the concepts, it also added to the teacher's instructional strategies for teaching difficult and abstract concepts. Teachers adopting the use of computer animation in abstract chemistry concepts teaching will enhance the efficiency of teaching-learning of chemistry concepts and assimilation of information.

Despite the importance of Mathematics, students may have difficulty studying the subject (Uwadiae, 2010), this may be due to the abstract approach employed in teaching the subject. Thus, this study anticipates that the implementation of an interactive whiteboard will be a game changer in terms of improving students' academic performance in Mathematics. On this premise, this study investigates the effect of the Interactive whiteboard on the academic performance of senior secondary school Mathematics students in Abua/Odual Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

The study of Mathematics in secondary schools in Nigeria appears to many students as a nightmare, because the only reason why they learn the subject is its being compulsory for students intending to pursue science-related careers. Subsequently, the perception of Mathematics is reflected in the

fluctuating statistics of students' performance reported by the West Africa Examination Council for 2007-2020.

The foregoing statistics do not only reveal the abysmal performance of students in Mathematics nationwide in terms of the fluctuating statistics, but they also reveal inconsistency in the trend of performance, a condition which may be attributed to the persistent use of traditional teaching methods in teaching Mathematics in schools in some states of the Federation including Rivers State. Could the integration of interactive whiteboards among others into the teaching of Mathematics improve students' performance in Mathematics? Consequent to the foregoing, this study investigates the effect of the Interactive White Board on the academic performance of secondary school Mathematics students in Abua/Odual Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

This study determined the effect of the Interactive whiteboard on the academic performance of senior secondary school Mathematics students in Abua/Odual Local Government Area, Rivers State. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. determine if secondary school students improved upon their performance in Mathematics due to the use of an Interactive whiteboard.
2. establish if mean performance differs between male and female secondary school students taught Mathematics due to the use of Interactive White Board

Research Questions

The following research questions will guide this study.

1. What are the mean performance scores of students taught Mathematics with interactive whiteboards and those taught with a conventional approach?
2. What are the mean performance scores of male and female students taught Mathematics with interactive whiteboards?

Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses formulated were tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the performance scores of students taught Mathematics with interactive whiteboards and those taught with conventional methods.
2. There is no significant difference in the performance scores of students taught Mathematics with interactive whiteboards based on gender.

Methods

The study adopted the quasi-experimental research design using a non-randomized-control group pre-test and post-test experimental group design. The population of the study is 6,961 students of all eleven (11) secondary school students in Abua/Odual Local Government Area of Rivers State. The Stratified random sampling technique was used to select a sample size of one hundred (100) students made up of fifty-three (53) males and forty-seven (47) females. The instrument for data collection is the Mathematics Performance Test (MPT). The MPT had ten (10) item questions. The face and content validity of the Mathematics Performance Test (MPT) was established by two experts in mathematics education and one in test and measurement. Kuda-Richardson (KR-21) method was used to test for the reliability of the instrument (MPT) and a reliable value was 0.73. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significant levels.

Data Presentation and Results

Research Question One: What are the mean performance scores of students taught Mathematics with interactive whiteboards and those taught with conventional?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of interactive whiteboards and conventional method on students' academic achievement

Group	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Conventional	50	55.54	1.11	56.06	1.12	0.52
Experimental	50	54.12	1.05	63.10	1.86	8.98

The result in Table 1 showed that the mean of students exposed to the interactive whiteboard approach was 63.10 (post-test) while those with the conventional teaching method had a mean of 56.06 for post-test. The mean gain is 0.52 for the conventional and 8.98 for the interactive whiteboard approach. This means that students exposed to the interactive whiteboard approach had a higher mean and performed better than the conventional teaching method.

Research Question Two: What are the mean performance scores of male and female students taught Mathematics with interactive whiteboards?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of mean performance scores of students using interactive whiteboards base on gender

Gender	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Male	25	54.28	1.12	64.09	1.15	9.81
Female	25	53.92	1.08	62.11	1.10	8.19

The results in Table 2 showed that the performance of Male students exposed to the interactive whiteboard approach obtained a mean score of 64.09 while their Female counterparts had a performance means score of 62.11. Their mean gain was 9.81 for males and 8.19 for females. It is therefore deduced that the performance of Male students had a higher mean score than the performance of their Female counterparts. Therefore, male students performed better than female students in interactive whiteboards.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the performance scores of students taught Mathematics with interactive whiteboards and those taught with conventional method.

Table 3: Analysis of one-way ANCOVA in the difference between the performance of students taught using interactive whiteboards approach and those taught using the conventional approach.

Dependent Variable: POSTTEST							
Source of Variance	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	P value	Partial Eta Squared	
Corrected Model	743.360 ^a	1	321.694	32.388	.000	.499	
Intercept	1673.222	1	1573.331	162.302	.000	.709	
GROUP	71.257	1	70.789	4.68	.011	0.416	
Error	624.433	98	8.944				
Total	32722.000	100					
Corrected Total	1289.000	99					

Table 3 showed that the calculated F-value for the group is 4.68 at degrees of freedom of 1 and 98 and it is significant at 0.011 probability level, since the p-value of 0.11 is less than 0.05 significant level, the null hypothesis one was therefore rejected. Therefore, there is a statistically significant difference in the performance scores of students taught Mathematics with interactive whiteboards and those taught with conventional methods.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the performance scores of students taught Mathematics with interactive whiteboards base on gender.

Table 4: Analysis of ANCOVA in the difference in performance of male and female students taught using interactive whiteboards approach.

Dependent Variable: POSTTEST						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	52.205 ^a	1	26.102	3.913	.032	.018
Intercept	831.034	1	831.034	124.591	.000	.007
Gender	8.751	1	8.751	5.12	.062	.001
Error	186.763	48	6.670			
Total	18143.000	50				
Corrected Total	238.968	49				

The results in Table 4 showed that the calculated F-value for the effect of gender is 5.12 at degrees of freedom of 1 and 48. The calculated p-value of 0.062 is more than the 0.05 significant level, therefore, the null hypothesis two is accepted, meaning; there is no significant difference in the performance scores of students taught Mathematics with interactive whiteboards based on gender. The Partial Eta squared is .001, which according to Cohen's proposal is no effect. This accounts for approximately 1%.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study were discussed in line with the research questions and hypotheses in the study in the following ways;

What are the mean performance scores of students taught Mathematics with interactive whiteboards and those taught with conventional?

The findings from table 1 and table 3 have shown that, students exposed to interactive whiteboards approach had a higher mean and performed better than the conventional teaching method. Also, there was a significant difference in the performance scores of students taught Mathematics with interactive whiteboards and those taught with conventional method. This result is in line with studies conducted by Ifeakor, Akujieze, and Erutujiro (2020) who found that the interactive whiteboard-based instructional model is superior to the lecture method in improving achievement among the students in mathematics. This outcome is most likely attributable to the fact that interactive whiteboards can significantly improve and deepen students' grasp of mathematics.

What is the mean performance scores of male and female students taught geometry using laboratory approach?

Results in table 2 revealed that male students performed better than female students in laboratory teaching approach. Also, tables 4 revealed a significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught geometry using laboratory approach. The outcome also harmonized with the findings of Janet (2017), Okigbo and Osuafor (2018) that found that male and female students performed different.

What is the mean performance scores of male and female students taught Mathematics with interactive whiteboards?

The results in table 2 and 4 showed that male students performed better than female students in interactive whiteboards approach. Likewise, table 4 shown that, there was no significant difference between male and female students performance scores when taught Mathematics with interactive whiteboards.

This result is in line to Egara and Mosimege (2024) concluded that the achievement and interest scores of male and female learners who received mathematics instruction using flipped classroom approach were the same.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the use of interactive whiteboards in teaching mathematics led to significant performance improvements regardless of gender. In other words, interactive whiteboards enhanced learning and boosted performance for all students.

Recommendation

The findings of this study were recommended based on the following:

1. Mathematics teachers should integrate interactive whiteboards into their lessons, as this approach can enhance students' grasp of mathematical concepts and contribute to improved exam performance.
2. Mathematics teachers should ensure that both male and female students have equal access to interactive whiteboards in their lessons. Doing so will enhance Mathematics performance for all students.

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